

Genecology and some information about this field.

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Abstract. This article reveals gynecology (history and modern) and its types, different diseases and their solutions.

Key words: gynecology, andrology, body, treatment, male reproductive system.

INTRODUCTION

Gynaecology or gynecology (see American and British English spelling differences) is the area of medicine that involves the treatment of women's diseases, especially those of the reproductive organs. It is often paired with the field of obstetrics, forming the combined area of obstetrics and gynaecology (OB-GYN).

The term comes from Greek and means "the science of women".[1][2] Its counterpart is andrology, which deals with medical issues specific to the male reproductive system.[3] The Kahun Gynaecological Papyrus, dated to about 1800 BC, deals with gynaecological diseases, fertility, pregnancy, contraception, etc. The text is divided into thirty-four sections, each section dealing with a specific problem and containing diagnosis and treatment; no prognosis is suggested. Treatments are non-surgical, comprising applying medicines to the affected body part or swallowing them. The womb is at times seen as the source of complaints manifesting themselves in other body parts.[5]

Ayurveda, an Indian traditional medical system, also provides details about concepts and techniques related to gynaecology.[6][7]

The Hippocratic Corpus contains several gynaecological treatises dating to the 5th and 4th centuries BC. Aristotle is another strong source for medical texts from the 4th century BC with his descriptions of biology primarily found in History of Animals, Parts of Animals, Generation of Animals.[8] The gynaecological treatise Gynaikēia by Soranus of Ephesus (1st/2nd century AD) is extant (together with a 6th-century Latin paraphrase by Muscio, a physician of the same school). He was the chief representative of the school of physicians known as the "methodists". In the medical schools of the early nineteenth century, doctors did not study female reproductive anatomy, seen as repulsive, nor train in pregnancy and childbirth

management. That women, because of their anatomy and the risks of the dangerous birthing process, had unique medical concerns and challenges, enough that a doctor might specialize in them, is an innovation widely credited to J. Marion Sims and to a lesser extent his trainee and partner Nathan Bozeman, physicians from Montgomery, Alabama. Sims is widely considered to be the father of modern gynaecology.[9] While there have been isolated precedents for some of his innovations, he was the first to have published on the Sims' position, the Sims' speculum, the Sims sigmoid catheter, and on gynecological surgery, first on repair of vesico-vaginal fistulas, a socially devastating consequence of protracted childbirth, at the time without treatment of any sort. He founded the first women's hospital in the country, first in his backyard in Montgomery, limited to Black enslaved women, then the Woman's Hospital of New York. He was elected president of the American Medical Association, and was the first American physician of whom a statue was erected..

Sims developed his new specialty using the bodies of enslaved women, who could not refuse the extended glance of any white male that cared to observe any part of their anatomy. They could not "consent" in the sense modern medical research requires. No one did.

At the time anesthesia was itself a research area, and the first experiments (in dentistry) were being published. Using early anesthesia (in 1845, say) was much more dangerous and difficult than it would be a century later. In addition, it was widely believed that Blacks did not feel pain as much as whites, and white women proved unable to endure the pain.

At the time, Sims was seen as a hero. Even his enemies, Bozeman chief among them, did not attack him for either experimenting on the enslaved, or for not using anesthesia. Abolitionists such as William Lloyd Garrison were quick to put in print any mistreatment of the enslaved; Garrison's influential *The Liberator* has been completely indexed, but it never mentions Sims. Nor does the digitized portion of the Black press mention him. When he left Alabama in 1853, a local newspaper called him "an honor to our state".[10]

Modern gynecology:

In the late 20th century, Sims has come to be villainized. Now criticized for his practices, Sims developed some of his techniques and instruments by operating on slaves, many of whom were not given anesthesia.[11][12] Sims performed surgeries on 12 enslaved women in his homemade backyard hospital for four years.

While performing these surgeries he invited eager physicians and students to watch invasive and painful procedures while the women were exposed. On one of the women, named Anarcha, he performed 30 surgeries without anesthesia.[13] Due to having so many enslaved women, he would rotate from one to another, continuously trying to perfect the repair of their fistulas. Physicians and students lost interest in assisting Sims over the course of his backyard practice, and he recruited other enslaved women, who were healing from their own surgeries, to assist him. In 1855, Sims went on to found the Woman's Hospital in New York, the first hospital specifically for female disorders.[14]

Diseases

Examples of conditions dealt with by a gynaecologist are:

Cancer and pre-cancerous diseases of the reproductive organs including ovaries, fallopian tubes, uterus, cervix, vagina, and vulva

Incontinence of urine[15]

Amenorrhoea (absent menstrual periods)

Endometriosis

Dysmenorrhoea (painful menstrual periods)

Infertility[16]

Menorrhagia (heavy menstrual periods); a common indication for hysterectomy

Prolapse of pelvic organs

Infections of the vagina (vaginitis), cervix and uterus (including fungal, bacterial, viral, and protozoal)

Pelvic inflammatory disease[17]

Urinary tract infections

Polycystic ovary syndrome

Premenstrual dysphoric disorder

Post-menopausal osteoporosis

Other vaginal diseases

There is some crossover in these areas. For example, a woman with urinary incontinence may be referred to a urologist.

Conclusion

As with all surgical specialties, gynaecologists may employ medical or surgical therapies (or many times, both), depending on the exact nature of the problem that they are treating. Pre- and post-operative medical management will often employ many standard drug therapies, such as antibiotics, diuretics,

antihypertensives, and antiemetics. Additionally, gynaecologists make frequent use of specialized hormone-modulating therapies (such as Clomifene citrate and hormonal contraception) to treat disorders of the female genital tract that are responsive to pituitary or gonadal signals.

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14.Wallace-Sanders, Kimberly (2002). *Skin Deep, Spirit Strong* (PDF). *Mastering the Female Pelvis*. Archived (PDF) from the original on 3 November 2019. Retrieved 1 December 2017. Technological and scientific development" (Young and Bush 2), but the majority of teachers still teach in the traditional manner. However, this paper does not state that none of these traditional manners are bad or hurtful the students. In opinion, they are proving to be useful even today. there are many opportunities for students to gain confidence in erudition English who learn the speech for more than just fun. For them, to go on pace with English language teaching and put on more assurance, they have to stride into the world of multimedia technology. Here, multimedia technology refers to computer-based interactive applications that use both the hardware and software, allowing people to share their ideas and in turn. It is a mishmash of text, graphics, animation, video and sound. Twenty first century is the age of globalization and information technology as Harry Samuels argues, "Much more recent developments in social media and information technology are taking dialecteducation in new directions". English is one of the imperative mediums of communication in the world, so it is important to learn the language. As a result, English lingo teaching has been one of the important subjects in education. In fact, there are more non-native than native speakers of the language. With the rapid growth of science and technology, the use of multimedia technology in language teaching has created a complimentary context for reforming and exploring English language preparation models inthe new age. This inclination features the use of audio, visual, and animation effects in the English language teaching classrooms. Multimedia technology plays a objector role in civilizing actions and initiatives of students and teaching end product in the classrooms. Thus, industrial innovations should Go hand in hand with the growth of English and change the way in which we Communicate. In fact, the growth of

the Internet has facilitated the growth of the English language. In this astuteness, computers are no longer the exclusive domains of a few individuals, but rather they are available to many. Teachers can use multimedia technology to create more colorful and stimulating language program. There are many techniques applicable in different forms to English language teaching situations that now intimidate "to undermine the classroom completely as a position of study". Some are useful for testing and distance education; some for teaching business English, spoken English, reading, listening or interpreting. the attitude of teaching should be to comprehend new technologies without charming over the role of the teacher and without 1St National Conference on Teaching Innovations and Enhancing Learning. Most significantly, the new technologies have been showing and disseminated so quickly that we cannot avoid their attraction and authority on all of us: both teachers and learners, even both native and non-native speakers of English. Analysis on Necessity of Application of Multimedia Technology to English Teaching To Cultivate Students' Interest in Study Nowadays, the stereotyped traditional teaching methods and environment are unpopular while multimedia technology featuring audio, visual animation effects naturally and humanely makes us more access to information above and beyond, with such characteristics as abundant-information and crossing time and space, multimedia technology offers a sense of truth and functions very well, which greatly cultivates students' interest and motivation in study and their involvement in class activities. To Promote Students' Communication Capacity Traditional teaching has hampered students' capacity to figure out certain language and also understanding to configuration, meaning and function of the language, and makes the students passive recipients of knowledge, So it is hard to achieve the objective of communication. With teachers' directions foremost students' thought patterns and motivating students' emotions, the multimedia technology seeks incorporation of teaching and learning and provides the students greater incentives, The PPT courseware activate students' thinking; the visual and brilliant courseware and help them to transforms English learning into capability development. And such in-class activities as group discussion, subject discussion, and debates can also offer more opportunities for statement among students and between teachers and students. So multimedia technology teaching has uniquely stirred students' hopeful thinking and communication skills in social perform. To Improve Teaching Effect Multimedia teachings enrich coaching content and make the best of class time and

break the “teacher-centered” teaching pattern and fundamentally improve class efficiency. Due to large classes it is tricky for the students to have speaking communication. The utilization of multi-media through lab materializes the individualized and co-operative teaching. The traditional teaching model mainly emphasized on teachers’ instruction, and the in sequence provided is limited due to traditional classes. On the divergent, multimedia technology goes beyond time and space, creates more vivid, visual, true environment for English learning, stimulates students’ initiatives and economizes class time meanwhile increases class information. Widens Students' Knowledge about the Culture of English The use of multimedia technology, "connected to the target culture", offers the students with more information than textbooks, and helps them to be familiar with cultural backgrounds and real-life language materials, which can attract the students to learning. Having the profuse information through the use of multimedia technology, the students can be operational with knowledge about the ethnicity of the target language. This brings about an information sharing occasion among students and makes them actively participate in the class. Activities that help the students to learn the language more quickly and effectively. To Improve Interaction between Teacher and Student Multimedia teaching stresses the role of students, and enhances the importance of “interaction” amid teachers and students. A major feature of multimedia teaching is to prepare and improve students’ ability to pay attention and speak, and to develop their communicative competence, During this process, the teacher’s role as a facilitator is particularly prominent. Using multimedia in background manufacture creates a good platform for the exchange between teachers and students, while at the same time providing a language environment that improves on the traditional classroom teaching model. In this way, teachers in the classroom no longer blindly input in sequence and force students to receive it in a passive way. To Provide Flexibility to Course Content In adding up, multimedia teaching is also flexible. It is obvious that the context can be twisted not only in the classroom, but also after class. Multimedia language teaching can also create a multimedia language environment for the principle of conducting language teaching. English teaching itself must spotlight on the management of teachers and be student-centered, which we believe is one of the principles for language teaching. Students are hop to have some evils in classroom teaching, which can be addressed under the guidance of teachers. In such circumstances, students can use the new technology to their lead, such as

manipulating the network to contact teachers, and receiving answers by email. Advantages of the Use As the multimedia technology becomes more readily available to all of us, it seems appropriate that the language teachers should integrate it into their lesson and appraisal scheduling in the same way they have been doing with video,! lm and computer assisted learning strategies. The students are surrounded by technology and this technology can provide interesting and new approaches to language teaching because "the use of technology for coaching and learning is moving their institution in the right direction". In this way, the teachers of English can take full advantage of technology to teach English in the non-native communication countries. the following are some of the important advantages of the use of multimedia technology Develops Students' Communicative Competence It is hard to accomplish the goal of learning English language through the traditional teaching because it hampers the students' aptitude to recognize the structure, meaning and function of the language. Such teaching method makes the students 1St National Conference on Teaching Innovations and Enhancing.

CONCLUSION

Concerning the progress of technology, we believe that in future, the use of multimedia English teaching will be added developed. The process of English learning will be more student-centered but less time-consuming. Therefore, itpromises that the teaching quality will be improved and students' applied English skill look into be effectively cultivated, meaning that students' communicative competence will be further developed. In end, we believe that this process can fully get better students' ideation and practical language skills, which is supportive and useful to ensure and fulfill an effective result of teaching and learning.

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